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EXPLORING PROFESSIONAL INTERESTS OF COMPUTER AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING FRESHMEN

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ABSTRACT

The fields of electrical and computer engineering are subjected to constant change regarding their domain knowledge. Technologies, programming languages, environments, and development approaches change reflecting industry needs and formal education programs. But it is not just what needs to be known that influences this change. It is also the interest of electrical and computer engineering students. Some of the factors affecting students' decisions about their profiling during their studies are their intrinsic motivation and interests, their career and pay prospects, but also hard limits like enrollment caps on a study program or availability of a potential mentor. This paper explores the interests of two consecutive generations of electrical and computer engineering freshmen regarding their future professional focus. Students' assignment was to choose and research a topic they would be interested to work on during their studies and find a potential mentor who could supervise their work. The answers collected from more than 600 students per generation regarding their chosen topic of interest were clustered to identify topics of most or least interest as well as changes in those topics between years. The interests that students have expressed are reflective of their perception of popular electrical and computer engineering topics like artificial intelligence or mobile app programming. Students' reported interests are discussed as information that can be useful for faculty-level decision-making, either to try to affect students' perceptions and interests for certain topics and study programs or to plan for restructuring.

1 INTRODUCTION

Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, artificial reality, and data mining are introducing many changes to related industries and it is not surprising that electrical and computer engineering professionals are in high demand. It is estimated that only

the artificial reality market will be worth around \$60 billion by 2020 [1] and that the combined value of the artificial reality and virtual reality markets together will be worth \$209 billion by 2022 [2]. Many countries, therefore, have recognized the need for educating future engineering professionals and have introduced measures to increase interest in STEM fields. Such outreach programs occur both in primary [3] and secondary education [4], [5], as research has suggested that general interest or previous experience with related topics is a frequently mentioned reason for studying electrical and computer engineering [6]. Still, predicting or learning about students' professional interests is also important after they get enrolled in a studying program. Mismatched enrollment caps on a study program or unsustainable (lack of) interest in specific engineering disciplines can yield undesired outcomes regarding the number of future engineering professionals. They can also affect a university's decisions to end some study modules or introduce new ones. It is, therefore, important to gain insight into students' interests after they enroll in an engineering program as well. In this paper, the first results of ongoing research of professional interests of first years' students at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of electrical engineering and computing are described. The reported results are based on the self-reported data from the 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 generations of students.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Assignment context

The data reported in this short paper were collected within the *Communication skills* course, a first-semester course concerned with communication skills relevant for future engineering professionals. The final course assignment worth 30% of the overall course credits requires students to create a two-minute video presentation about a topic they would like to work on during their studies. The chosen topic must be related to the faculty and students are also required to find a potential mentor for their work. The mentor must be a member of the faculty who either teaches a course related to the topic of interest, has that topic listed under their areas of expertise at their personal university webpage, has already mentored students on similar topics, or is listed at the university webpage as a collaborator on at least one scientific project related to that topic. Students are instructed not to contact their potential mentor since they are doing this assignment for practice and to start thinking about their professional interests. Students are also instructed to make their topic as specific as possible and to avoid too general topics such as *machine learning* or *data mining* without a specific application. The submitted video should contain a brief introduction to the chosen topic, a description of its importance, the link to the potential mentor, and, if possible, an idea of how the author wants to contribute to it.

Students' answers containing the proposed assignment topics and the name of a potential mentor were collected using Moodle and exported for analysis. A total of 650 and 672 topic/mentor pairs were submitted in the academic years of 2019/2020 and 2020/2021, respectively. To get an overview of students' interests, submitted topics were read by course lecturers and main topic categories were defined within the two

main studying programs: computer engineering and electrical engineering. Approximately 50 categories were derived based on students' submitted topics and those categories were further generalized to reduce their number and to increase the number of included topics. For some topics, it was difficult to assess where does the contribution lies, *i.e.* which category should a topic be assigned to. For example, in the development of a specific mobile application or in the development of an electrical sensor device that will supply it with data. More than one category could have been assigned to a topic in that case, but this happened relatively rarely. Finally, only the categories with at least 10 entries either in 2019/2020 or 2020/2021 were included in this report.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis for both years are displayed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Most common topics for two generations of students

Based on the results displayed in Fig. 1, several topics have emerged as most common in both academic years, specifically: machine learning (especially for games and detection/classification problems), mobile application development (especially learning and everyday apps), and artificial intelligence (typically in games, recommender systems, autonomous vehicles, and drones navigation). It seems that approximately 45% of students have an interest in one of those three topics. This is not surprising given the hype associated with artificial intelligence which generally includes machine learning and computer vision. Mobile and web applications, on the other hand, are ubiquitous today and students probably expect that that demand will continue to thrive, making their development a well-paid job. Robotics (including the design of humanoid robots, robot arms, and drones) seems to be the highest-ranked topic related to electrical engineering. Other notable topics in that category include

electrical vehicles, energy systems, and sensors and their applications. Still, those four topics related to the electrical engineering study program have only been selected by approximately 20% of students. Those results are also consistent with an already noted decrease in enrolment of the electrical engineering program at the Faculty. Interestingly, categories like artificial reality, bioinformatics, or quantum computing all fall below the 10 entries threshold in both generations of students although they seem to offer challenges that will be very relevant in the near future. Those topics might offer additional opportunities for students or will remain underrepresented due to the popularity of artificial intelligence and machine learning.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the first results of a work in progress aiming to document the interests and the changes in the professional interests of engineering students before and after they start an engineering degree. The acquired data suggest a larger interest in computing-related topics associated with artificial intelligence, machine learning, mobile application development, and robotics but at the same time underrepresentation of other relevant and generally popular topics like bioinformatics or artificial reality. If those trends show to be constant across generations of students, additional advertising, or outreach programs for such topics early during the studies might help students develop an interest in them.

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